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Raising standards for stakeholder engagement in Nature-based Solutions: Navigating the why, when, who and how

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ABSTRACT

Working with people is inherent to Nature-Based Solutions (NbS). The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions (NbS) requires interventions to work with and for society, acknowledging and integrating stakeholder views in all aspects of NbS in landscapes. However, existing guidance on NbS does not fully reflect all the insights and guidance available from an extensive literature on stakeholder engagement, empowerment, participation and related concepts. This paper provides guidance on achieving stakeholder engagement in NbS, by using the literature to analyse the role of stakeholder engagement in eight NbS criteria of the IUCN Global Standard. Each criterion represents themes orienting engagement, briefly: (1) societal challenges, (2) design at scale, (3) biodiversity net-gain, (4) economic feasibility, (5) inclusive governance, (6) balancing trade-off (7) adaptive management and (8) sustainability and mainstreaming. We show it is imperative to clearly differentiate stakeholders and their differing roles in different aspects of NbS. Hence, for each criterion there should be: a clearly defined rationale (why), the different stakeholder groups (who), the stage of the project (when) and the appropriate pathways (how) by which stakeholders will be engaged. We conclude with a discussion on the implications of the framework for those planning, resourcing and enabling nature-based solutions. We emphasise stakeholder engagement as multidimensional, requiring reflexivity and attention to inclusivity, equity and transparency. We also highlight the wicked problems of stakeholder engagement, in terms of the need for political support, resource commitment and competence to make engagement in NbS fit-for-purpose.

1. Introduction

The increasing scope and scale of environmental challenges such as pollution, biodiversity degradation, climate change, flood and drought risks, and socio-economic challenges such as food insecurity and poor human health have amplified policy and scholarly interest in Nature-Based Solutions (NbS). NbS is endorsed by current global policy frameworks and conventions, such as the Global Biodiversity Framework (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2000). The fifth United Nations Environmental Assembly defined NbS as “actions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage natural or modified terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine ecosystems, which address social, economic and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while simultaneously providing human well-being, ecosystem services and resilience and biodiversity benefits” (UNEP, 2022, p. 2). Seddon et al. (2021) categorized these ‘actions’ as protection, restoration, management and creation of nature.

NbS is closely related to ecosystem-based approaches, green infrastructure and ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2019; Faivre et al., 2017; Fisher et al., 2021). These approaches are expected to safeguard and improve the delivery of many ecosystem services (IPBES, 2019) and be relevant to many economic sectors, including agriculture and water supply (Convention on Wetlands, 2021; WWAP, 2018). Hence, they are part of the transformative actions required to address environmental, ecological and socio-economic challenges (Palomo et al., 2021; Welden et al., 2021).

In 2020, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) published a Global Standard for NbS (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2019; IUCN, 2020b) to support globally consistent understanding and implementation of NbS. Definitions of NbS vary, but the IUCN Global Standard for NbS (hereafter called the IUCN Standard) is increasingly dominant in academia and practice (Châles et al., 2023; Le Gouvello et al., 2023; Welden et al., 2021), as it has been carefully crafted to take account of different contexts and objectives. The IUCN standard

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comprises 28 indicators, grouped under eight core criteria, complemented by explanation and guidance (IUCN, 2020a, 2020b). These criteria are that NbS should (1) address societal challenges; (2) be designed at landscape scales; (3) enhance biodiversity; (4) achieve economic feasibility; (5) work inclusively and transparently; (6) balance trade-offs equitably; (7) be managed adaptively with evidence; and (8) be sustained and mainstreamed. These criteria reflect principles for resilient natural resource management that reflects societal needs – and should be prominent in organising and appraising NbS.

The fifth criterion states that “NbS are based on inclusive, transparent and empowering governance processes” (IUCN, 2020b, p. 14). This criterion highlights the need to engage stakeholders to ensure their concerns are recognized, addressed and included in NbS. As evident in the IUCN Standard, addressing the increasing socio-economic and environmental challenges with NbS requires a deliberate effort across multiple scales and sectors and consideration of diverse knowledge and experiences (Calliari et al., 2019; Mabon et al., 2022; Woroniecki et al., 2020). Implementing NbS at landscape scale could be more complex because of the diverse and sometimes conflicting stakeholder interests (Giordano et al., 2020).

Research suggests that opening up stakeholder engagement can reveal diverse values and understandings, which may not align with each other or with existing bureaucratic structures (Akhmouch and Clavreul, 2017; Ayala-Orozco et al., 2018; Ferreira et al., 2020; Waylen et al., 2015). Additionally, ‘stakeholders’ include various societal groups affected by or influencing a problem and its responses (Reed et al., 2009), so engagement often requires working with many groups in diverse ways. Therefore, achieving high-quality stakeholder engagement in NbS will encounter many challenges. If NbS are to be effective alternatives to conventional measures, engagement must be done thoughtfully. Codified approaches can help ensure inclusivity, while reflexive, situational engagement is preferable to predefining stakeholders in complex situations.

Although some NbS literature (Kiss et al., 2022; Malekpour et al., 2021; Zingraff-Hamed et al., 2020) has drawn attention to the importance of stakeholder engagement, there is limited understanding of how upscaling of NbS within the landscape and across multiple policy jurisdictions evokes complexity, which could be addressed deliberately through a careful stakeholder engagement. The IUCN Standard recognises stakeholder engagement as one of the eight (8) essential criteria to guide NbS planning and management. However, stakeholder engagement is inherent to all eight (8) criteria. The different criteria could be opportunities to carefully choose stakeholders and identify appropriate means to engage them while navigating the emerging challenges.

This paper seeks to enhance the current approach to stakeholder engagement in planning, implementing and managing NbS by addressing the challenges of diverse stakeholder interests in landscape-based NbS. Our novel contribution is to show that combining the IUCN NbS standard with guidance on why, who, when and how to engage stakeholders creates a framework that reveals the complexities and power of situated stakeholder engagement. Based on the IUCN NbS standard, we highlight that engagement requires diverse expertise – not just project leads or social scientists but also ecologists, engineers, and economists – to tackle issues like economic feasibility, fairness, and biodiversity in NbS.

To develop this framework, we build on socio-ecological systems and participatory theories in NbS, alongside insights from the EU Guideline on co-creation and co-governance of NbS (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023). While our framework centers on the IUCN Global Standard, we acknowledge the EU Guideline’s complementary insights into stakeholder engagement in NbS, drawing on similar foundational literature.

The following section presents the framework using the IUCN’s eight NbS criteria as key themes for planning stakeholder engagement. Each criterion examines the rationale (why), stakeholders involved (who), project stages (when), and engagement pathways (how). Section 3

applies the framework to show implications for each criterion, while Section 4 discusses broader implications for planning and enabling NbS. Section 5 concludes with the strengths and limitations of framework and future research directions.

2. A framework for engaging stakeholders in NbS

This manuscript draws on targeted searches of peer-reviewed (see Supplementary Material 1) and grey literature, as well as the authors’ experience in the EU Horizon 2020 MERLIN project, which applied the IUCN Global Standard for NbS. Our framework for stakeholder engagement is informed by NbS, environmental, and resource management studies, offering insights into engagement pathways, rationales, and stakeholder types. For each IUCN criterion, we selected NbS studies and case studies to illustrate specific engagement practices.

Stakeholder engagement refers to “efforts to ensure that individuals and groups and organisations have the opportunity to take part in the decision-making and implementation processes that affect them or in which they have an interest” (OECD, 2015b, p. 32). This study is inspired by socio-ecological systems (Walker et al., 2004) and deliberative participatory theories (Bächtiger et al., 2018). NbS are socio-ecological systems because their implementation and management attract diverse social, economic, political, and ecological interests across scales, especially in complex landscapes (Malekpour et al., 2021; Seddon et al., 2020). Thus, a transdisciplinary approach is essential to integrate diverse perspectives in NbS (Tzoulas et al., 2021). Deliberate participation also enables explicit planning and adopting of stakeholder engagement (Meadow et al., 2015).

Our framework combines these two theoretical foundations for practice-oriented stakeholder engagement in NbS (Fig. 1) without a deeper analysis of each theory. We view the IUCN NbS criteria as diverse socio-ecological themes around which stakeholders may have direct or indirect interests. Hence, engagement initiatives may focus on specific aspects, such as balancing trade-offs (e.g. Giordano et al., 2020), economic feasibility (e.g. Mok et al., 2021) or monitoring (van der Jagt et al., 2023). For deliberate participation, we identify four building

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework for stakeholder engagement in each IUCN NbS criterion. Each criterion defines the key issues and themes around which stakeholders could be engaged. Engagement around Why, Who, When and How runs through each NbS criteria.

blocks: the first and central building block comprises the rationale (why) for engaging stakeholders on each IUCN criterion, followed by defining stakeholders (who), project stage (when), and pathways (how). Recent publications on co-creation and co-governance in NbS underscore the importance of these building blocks (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023).

Combining the IUCN criteria with each building block may appear complex. However, the complexity requires engagement to be reflexive (*adapting to challenges of each NbS criteria*) and situational (*addressing varying stakeholder motivations*) (Murunga, 2022). Clarifying these complexities can help avoid ambiguity and make engagement more effective (Malekpour et al., 2021; Murunga, 2022).

2.1. Why seek stakeholder engagement in each of the NbS criteria?

This question pertains to the rationale of engagement in each NbS criterion. A clear, rationale is essential for meaningful engagement (Akhmouch and Clavreul, 2017; Ayala-Orozco et al., 2018). These rationales can be substantive, normative or instrumental (Blackstock and Richards, 2007; Stirling, 2006; Stirling, 2007). Substantively, engagement allows exploration of alternative solutions with stakeholder insights (Malekpour et al., 2021), improving NbS decisions and outcomes. It also offers stakeholders and project leads a learning basis for decision-making, enables suitable engagement approaches, and helps address grievances (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2019). For example, when win-win outcomes are unfeasible, engagement enables discussion of trade-offs and compromises (Seddon et al., 2020).

Instrumentally, engagement could enable stakeholders to better understand the project's benefits, further build trust and increase acceptance and ownership of the initiative. Ultimately, acceptance could lead to stewardship and greater sustainability when stakeholders' capacity is built to implement and manage the NbS (Blackstock and Richards, 2007; Kiss et al., 2022).

Normatively, good governance principles (such as OECD, 2015a; UN ESCAP, 2009) call for fair, transparent stakeholders engagement. In particular, the success and acceptance of NbS in the landscape rely on a diverse stakeholders with varying interests across different sectors and spatial scales (Bark et al., 2021; Ibrahim et al., 2020, 2023). Engagement in each NbS criteria could help integrate these interests for fair representation.

The engagement rationale (why) shapes decisions on who to engage and how to engage them. For deliberate engagement to be reflexive and situational, our framework emphasises the need for explicit and clear rationales for each NbS criterion. Lack of clarity can lead to difficulty in prioritizing objectives, reduced stakeholder commitment, and increased tensions (Blackstock and Richards, 2007; Blackstock et al., 2014). Moreover, the rationales may evolve over project phases (Malekpour et al., 2021). For instance, engaging stakeholders on biodiversity enhancement may differ from engagement on societal challenges (see Section 3), and an initial focus on exploring project alternatives may later evolve to addressing grievances.

2.2. Who should be engaged in NbS process?

Stakeholders are "persons or groups who are directly or indirectly affected by a project, as well as those who may have interests in a project and/or the ability to influence its outcome, either positively or negatively" (Sequeira and Warner, 2007, p. 10). Depending on the setting and issues at stake, stakeholders could include public authorities, private entities, academic experts, civil organizations, politicians, the media, and individual citizens (Arlati et al., 2021; Mok et al., 2021; Zingraff-Hamed et al., 2020). Addressing 'who' usually requires a thorough analysis of stakeholders and their interests, influences and potential roles (Reed et al., 2009; Vogler et al., 2017; Zingraff-Hamed et al., 2020), which will vary depending on the engagement rationale (why). Therefore, in a single NbS project, there is the potential to engage

different stakeholders for different NbS criteria (Malekpour et al., 2021). More importantly, it is possible for new stakeholders who were not engaged in a particular NbS criterion to emerge in other criteria. This framing aligns with the call for situational engagement by understanding the circumstances that may encourage or discourage stakeholders from participating in the decision-making process (Murunga, 2022). While some stakeholders may be interested in biodiversity, others may be interested only in the economic feasibility. Hence, discussing economic issues with stakeholders interested in biodiversity may be counterproductive. However, a situational approach could enable stakeholders to articulate their views and interests and ask questions about issues of concern.

2.3. How should stakeholders be engaged?

This question refers to the type, methods and pathways of engaging stakeholders. The literature (e.g. Arlati et al., 2021; Fors et al., 2021; Mahmoud et al., 2021; Puskás et al., 2021) usually address this question by fully or partly adopting the Spectrum of Public Participation (SPP) (IAP2, 2018) or the Arnstein's Ladder of participation. We synthesise their categorisations into four main pathways (Fig. 2):

- **Informing:** A one-way communication resulting in a tokenistic engagement.
- **Consulting:** A limited 2-way communication involving acquisition of information and feedback from stakeholders and answering their questions.
- **Collaborating and co-deciding:** Multiple communication involving partnerships with stakeholders.
- **Delegating:** Multiple communication offering stakeholders the opportunity to lead in making decisions.

Our framework does not prioritize a particular pathway over others since different stakeholders require different engagement pathways depending on their expertise, interests and influence (dos Muchangos et al., 2017; Murunga, 2022). Hence, the pathways should be fit for purpose based on the rationale (why), project stage (when) and stakeholder group (who). While engagement at the upper spectrum is more intensive and ensures stakeholders are part of the process (Mahmoud et al., 2021), the pathways at the bottom could help educate and get the stakeholders to accept, debate or contribute to some interventions and move up the ladder for other activities. Hence, based on the engagement rationale, each NbS criteria could have multiple engagement pathways for the different stakeholder groups.

Murunga (2022) recognized the pathways as informing, consulting and participating, while Menny et al. (2018) considered them as

Fig. 2. Pathways of stakeholder engagement (How). Top of the ladder demonstrate intensive engagement, while bottom of the ladder is less intensive.

informing, consulting and co-creating. Nevertheless, the pathway adopted will determine the specific methods for engaging stakeholders (Fors et al., 2021). Since the upper spectrum is multi-way communication, the method can include steering groups and stakeholder forums. The bottom spectrum can adopt lectures, webinars, interviews and questionnaires to communicate with stakeholders (Juárez-Bourke and Blackstock, 2021).

2.4. When should stakeholders be engaged in NbS?

This question aligns with the call for stakeholders to be engaged in each stage of the NbS project (Raymond et al., 2017). Urban green space literature (Fors et al., 2021; Fors et al., 2015) identified four strategic project stages, comprising planning, designing, construction and maintaining. In NbS literature (Ferreira et al., 2020; Mahmoud and Morello, 2018; Martin et al., 2021; Menny et al., 2018), the common terms used include define (initiate), design (plan), implement (develop), monitor and evaluate. We synthesize these into five iterative phases of the NbS process:

- **Problem definition:** identifying challenges, opportunities and potential solutions (Raymond et al., 2017).
- **Project design:** grasping the context of NbS and designing and developing activities (Menny et al., 2018).
- **Project implementation:** putting the design ideas into practice (Menny et al., 2018)
- **Project management and maintenance:** Operating, using and keeping the project going (Fisher et al., 2021)
- **Monitoring and evaluation:** assessing and learning from the outcomes (Menny et al., 2018).

Engaging stakeholders throughout these stages is often labelled as co-creation (Mahmoud and Morello, 2018), with each stage occurring through co-define, co-design, co-managing and co-monitoring (European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023), respectively. Therefore, these stages help to know when the engagement around the NbS criteria could occur regarding how to organise the engagement and who to include. Hence, we consider which of these stages could be used to engage stakeholders for each NbS criterion.

3. Application: engaging stakeholders through the lenses of the IUCN Global Standard for NbS

This section uses the literature with NbS examples to illustrate how different NbS criteria (Sections 3.1–3.8) influence stakeholder engagement. We emphasise why (the rationale), who (stakeholder types), how (the pathways) and when (project stage) as the building blocks (Table 1). Since the building blocks, including the different types of rationale, are intertwined, we analyse them together instead of separating them to avoid repetition.

3.1. Societal challenges

Societal challenges addressed by NbS include climate threats, water security, economic development and environmental degradation (IUCN, 2020b). Stakeholder engagement around this criterion is important (why) so that challenges are defined jointly during NbS definition (when) (Martin et al., 2021). This is critical because there is the risk of project initiators and implementers identifying challenges not well-understood by the stakeholders or aligned with their aspirations. For example, in the Alpine Isar River (Germany) flood risk management project, leads pre-conceived the focus to be flood mitigation (Martin et al., 2021). However, public engagement highlighted recreational, social, and biodiversity needs. While the project proceeded to address floods, integrating these other issues enabled a multifunctional project.

Table 1

Definition of rationale (why) and possible types of stakeholders (who), pathways of engagement (how) and project stages to engage (when) to engagement stakeholders.

NbS Criteria	Why (Rational for engagement) S – Substantive; I – Instrumental; N – Normative.	Who (Kind of stakeholder) & How (Pathways of engagement)	When (Project stage of engagement)
Societal challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Gain understanding of how different stakeholders view the challenges to be addressed and their complexity. • N: Ensure related issues and grievances are considered. • S: Co-define and identify challenges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult Citizens and volunteer groups. • Collaborate with municipal authorities, environmental coalitions, pressure groups, environmental, nature reserve and biodiversity department. 	Problem definition for all stakeholders.
Design & implement at scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Defining objectives, sectors and spatial scales with stakeholders. • S: Identifying alternative design solutions and implementation procedures by considering socio-economic conditions. • S: Have a broader awareness of NbS beneficiaries. • S: Facilitate knowledge sharing around the design of the NbS. • N: Incorporate knowledge and interests of stakeholders from different sectors and spatial scales. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform wider citizens. • Consult environmental coalitions and pressure groups. • Collaborate with or delegate roles to volunteer groups & citizen representatives. • Collaborate with or delegate roles to municipal and local councils, environmental and biodiversity and planning departments. 	Project design to assess alternatives; Project implementation
Biodiversity net-gain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Gain expert group appraisal to ensure the biodiversity net-gain is profound and worth investment. • I: Develop shared understanding of the benefits of biodiversity to human wellbeing. • I: Increase support, acceptance and understanding of biodiversity benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform wider citizens. • Consult or collaborate with mediators and academics. • Collaborate with Individual champions and Municipal Authorities. • Delegate roles to Indigenous groups, Environmental and Biodiversity Departments, Environmental coalitions and pressures groups and Volunteer 	Problem definition; project design; project implementation

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

NbS Criteria	Why (Rational for engagement) <i>S – Substantive; I – Instrumental; N – Normative.</i>	Who (Kind of stakeholder) & How (Pathways of engagement)	When (Project stage of engagement)
Economic Feasibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Develop a shared understanding of cost-benefits to stakeholders. • S: Collaborate to identify funding instruments. • S: Address and assess externalities resulting from NbS and tolerance level of economic risks. • N: Include different values to identify a more holistic valuation. • N: Clarify accountability for funding and associated activities. 	<p>groups & citizen representatives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult wider citizens, Environmental and Biodiversity Departments. • Collaborate with Municipal and local councils, Mediators and Individual Champions. • Delegate roles Private Investors and Public funding agencies. 	<p>Problem definition; project design; project implementation</p>
Inclusive governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Increase awareness of stakeholders' own responsibilities. • S: Establish the basis for empowering less-empowered stakeholders where relevant. • I: Identify stakeholders needing empowerment. • I: Help to build trust and mutual understanding. • N: Ensure that no relevant stakeholder is left behind. • N: Get stakeholder views about the engagement/governance process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform wider citizens, volunteer groups and citizen representatives. • Consult property/landowners. • Collaborate with Municipal/local councils, mediators and academics. 	<p>Problem definition, project design; implementation; management and maintenance; monitoring and evaluation.</p>
Balance Trade-off	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Detect and understand trade-offs between beneficiaries. • I: Dialogue with all stakeholders affected and resolve potential conflicts and opposition. • N: Address feedback and grievance of stakeholders. • N: Acknowledge rights and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult wider citizens, volunteer groups, citizen representatives, environmental and biodiversity departments, Environmental coalitions, pressure groups. • Collaborates with mediators and academics. • Delegate roles with property/landowners and 	<p>Project design; implementation; management and maintenance</p>

Table 1 (continued)

NbS Criteria	Why (Rational for engagement) <i>S – Substantive; I – Instrumental; N – Normative.</i>	Who (Kind of stakeholder) & How (Pathways of engagement)	When (Project stage of engagement)
Adaptive management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Co-evaluate and monitor performance. • S: Learn from stakeholders as well. • S: Help to account for other outcomes from stakeholders' perspective. • I: Improve stakeholders' capacity to lead future maintenance activities. 	<p>responsibilities for sectoral and spatial representation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult wider citizens. • Collaborate with Volunteer groups, citizen representatives, Environmental coalitions and pressure groups, public funding agencies and Environmental and biodiversity departments. 	<p>indigenous groups.</p> <p>Project implementation, Management and maintenance; monitoring and evaluation.</p>
Sustainability & mainstreaming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S: Highlight lessons and engagement approaches for mainstreaming and transforming. • S: Share data for scaling up and contribute to a paradigm shift. • I: Promote wider citizen acceptance of the NbS concept. • I: Boost stakeholder confidence. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform wider citizens, volunteer groups and citizen representatives. • Consult Private investors, mediators and individual champions. • Delegate roles to Municipal and local councils, environmental, biodiversity and planning departments. 	<p>Managing and maintaining, monitoring and evaluation</p>

Therefore, apart from identifying the challenges, engagement helped incorporate different needs and multifaceted grievances, clearly understand societal challenges at the outset, and consider the most pressing societal issues in NbS.

Key stakeholders (*who*) under this criterion include citizen and environmental coalitions and municipal authorities. Environmental coalitions will help highlight ecological issues faced by the society. The essential pathways (*how*) for engaging such stakeholders are consultation and collaboration to allow their perspectives to be incorporated. Collaboration can occur if stakeholders strongly acknowledge that NbS is necessary (Malekpour et al., 2021). For instance, the Wolong National Nature Reserve adopted innovative governance measures through collaboration with pressure groups, which enabled NbS as an alternative to grey infrastructure (Martin et al., 2021). Also, Adelaide's River Torrens Linear Park project (Australia) was initiated after local councils collaborated to draw the state government's attention to the environmental and flood risks associated with the river (Ibrahim et al., 2023).

3.2. Design and implement at scale

Engaging stakeholders around designing and implementation at scale helps (*why*) to inform stakeholders about project goals, understand their interests and integrate them into the project design (Mahmoud and Morello, 2018; Mahmoud et al., 2021). In particular, engagement can build upon the problem definition stage to co-design the project with stakeholders who can help identify favoured options for scaling up (*why*

and when). This may promote a shared vision amongst stakeholders and help to specify project objectives (Menny et al., 2018). Engagement will also enable stakeholders to understand NbS practicalities, contribute to and provide feedback about actual implementation, and manage challenging issues (Menny et al., 2018; Raymond et al., 2017). While it was not widespread in the literature, the process also offers the opportunity to delineate the sectoral issues in the NbS.

Key stakeholders (*who*) under this criterion include citizens, environmental coalitions and public agencies (e.g. Mahmoud and Morello, 2021; Menny et al., 2018). Environmental coalitions are often influential in advocating for NbS and ensuring that ecological issues are considered (i.e. solutions are nature-based and benefit biodiversity). Municipal authorities are essential in facilitating the entire process.

The essential pathway (*how*) for engaging such stakeholders is collaboration to allow their perspectives to be incorporated. For instance, the Wolong National Nature Reserve collaborated with pressure groups, which enabled NbS as an alternative to grey infrastructure (Martin et al., 2021). Consultation was also common in the design and implementation stages. Indeed, consulting stakeholders is vital because of their informed opposition to measures with possible negative impacts on the environment (*how, who and why*), as in the River Torrens Linear Park project in Adelaide, Australia (Ibrahim et al., 2020, 2023). Such stakeholders could also act as agents of change and attract the support of wider stakeholders (Martin et al., 2021). Importantly, local governments and residents' councils should be consulted early in the project stages (*when*) to strengthen the likelihood of collaborative processes being undertaken (Mahmoud et al., 2021).

In the Alpine Isar River flood risk management example, while the general public and sectors such as tourism (*who*) with less influence on the projects were consulted (*how*) in co-defining the challenges (*why*), they were only informed during the design stage (*when*) (Martin et al., 2021). In the Wolong National Nature Reserve example, however, the public (*who*) was consulted through interviews, surveys and meetings (*how*). Moreover, the EU-funded PHUSICOS and CLEVER cities projects show that field trips with core stakeholders are important means of consultation (Cantergiani et al., 2019; Lupp et al., 2021). The rationale of consultation is usually to identify the design solution preferred by the citizens and communities (Arlati et al., 2021).

In some cases, community groups impacted by a project (*who*) will need to be empowered (*how*) to collaborate in the co-design of the NbS (*why and when*) (Willems et al., 2020). For instance, the EU-funded CLEVER Cities project in Hamburg (Germany) and Milano (Italy) had multiple cases of citizen delegation and collaboration (Arlati et al., 2021; Mahmoud and Morello, 2018). These were necessary because the project was customized to fit specific local contexts, and the local stakeholders were influential and highly affected. In the Urban Living Labs (ULLs) project of Alby (Sweden), citizen groups such as schools and youth clubs were consulted, and engagement with residents' councils involved questionnaires, enabling them to provide feedback regarding the project design (Menny et al., 2018). Nevertheless, in many of the so-called delegating pathways, final decisions were made by the project leaders and the actual implementation sometimes had limited citizen involvement (Menny et al., 2018). The reason for such limitation is the notion that project implementation (*when*) does not require in-depth citizen involvement (*who and how*) (Willems et al., 2020).

3.3. Biodiversity net-gain

This criterion aims to enhance biodiversity while addressing ecosystem degradation (IUCN, 2020a). A rationale (*why*) for identifying and engaging stakeholders who affect biodiversity is to increase support for embedding biodiversity gains in the overall NbS goals (de Koning et al., 2023). Key to this is biodiversity and conservancy departments, given their primary roles and statutory goals (*who*). For instance, the Municipal Biodiversity Department in Barcelona helped to integrate ecological goals into the design and implementation of Barcelona's first

Green Corridor, despite the project being initially intended for regenerating the urban area and enhancing civic outcomes (Kotsila et al., 2021).

For some stakeholders, the pathway (*how*) may not require high-level engagement or working closely with them. As for the other criteria, de Koning et al. (2023) argued that delegation is only required when stakeholders demonstrate their potential to conserve social and environmental integrity. Engaging such stakeholders can unearth new values, linked to concepts such as civic ecology and grassroot measures to support biodiversity and conservation (Puskás et al., 2021).

While citizen and indigenous group involvement is considered innovative, the aim is to engage stakeholders who place high values on biodiversity (*who*) because those who do not may negatively influence the engagement (*why*) (de Koning et al., 2023). Community engagement could occur through nature conservancies functioning as intermediaries to facilitate and lead initiatives (*how*) that enhance and integrate biodiversity into NbS (*who and why*) (Frantzeskaki and Bush, 2021). For instance, Greater Manchester inner city community groups used voluntary measures to establish community gardens to improve biodiversity, although this reportedly depended on the support of higher-level authorities (Dennis and James, 2016). Finally, champions such as local elected officials who value biodiversity can be identified as key intermediaries to help establish biodiversity frameworks at local and landscape levels. One example is the Metropolitan Forest Strategy of Melbourne, Australia, where a councillor played this role (Frantzeskaki and Bush, 2021). However, progress can be compromised if a new official's priorities divert attention from biodiversity goals.

3.4. Economic feasibility

The general rationale (*why*) for engaging stakeholders in this criterion is to establish the cost-benefits of the NbS while identifying an appropriate funding model and requirements for running the project (Mayor et al., 2021). Engagement could also help place a monetary value on the NbS benefits and costs and determine whether such values support investment.

Three key stakeholder groups (*who*) can be identified: public authorities, investors (representing private finance) and the citizens who may be beneficiaries. Those most relevant to be engaged under this criterion are the stakeholders who might benefit most from the NbS and are willing to commit resources. These beneficiaries will most likely be determined during the problem definition and design stages (*when*).

Collaboration is often viewed as the appropriate engagement pathway (*how*) to generate an accurate valuation and gauge willingness to commit funding (Mok et al., 2021). Public funding departments and investors need collaboration because they have strong interests in NbS valuation, are likely to benefit or lose most in the investment and can identify the best funding sources (*who, how and why*) (Egusquiza et al., 2019; Mayor et al., 2021; Mok et al., 2021). Other important stakeholders to collaborate with include water resources, planning, and environmental authorities because NbS could help them fulfil their legal responsibilities to protect the environment.

Mok et al. (2021) have suggested that communities can be excluded from the discussion of funding models because they are not the direct capital investors in NbS. However, communities need to be consulted when funding relies on taxes, user fees or donations or to understand their preferred business model for implementing NbS. For instance, in a consultation process for a Business Plan for Newcastle's Parks, communities preferred the city authority to fund the project instead of a new business approach that could lead to privatization of the parks (Kiss et al., 2022). Moreover, consulting the wider public could inform a more holistic valuation of the long-term benefits of NbS projects.

3.5. Inclusive governance

We frame this criterion as 'engagement about engagement process'.

Hence the engagement rationale (*why*) includes evaluating stakeholders' perception of the engagement processes to then enhance stakeholder participation. According to Lupp et al. (2021), to consider issues such as awareness raising, demonstration of NbS benefits and viable business models for NbS (*why*), stakeholders in the EU-funded PHUSICOS project revealed that they expect a collaborative process. Another rationale is to identify *who* to engage based on the interests and influence of specific stakeholders. For instance, in an NbS project in Brabham (Western Australia), the project developer, landowner and a state government body jointly identified another research organisation as an independent body to lead the entire collaboration for the project (*why*) (Malekpour et al., 2021).

Stakeholders (*who*) with a strong interest in collaborative (*how*) processes could be more actively engaged (Malekpour et al., 2021). Hence, governments, businesses, industry and citizen groups need collaboration depending on their influence and interest in each NbS criterion. For instance, if a project is led by an industry, that industry could lead the engagement process and further attract the involvement of communities. In other situations, engagement around this criterion could examine the alternative and creative approaches for empowering interested stakeholders with less influence (*why and how*). For instance, in a CLEVER Cities project (Arlati et al., 2021), a kick-off meeting pulled together different stakeholders, following which specific and interested stakeholders were registered as members of an urban innovative partnership to co-create NbS. This rationale could be framed to enhance the equitable participation of all stakeholders (Malekpour et al., 2021).

3.6. Balance trade-offs

Engagement in this criterion is required to understand different views, values, and preferences accorded to NbS and detect the potential trade-offs between beneficiaries (*why*) (Giordano et al., 2020). This criterion could rely on the findings from engagement in Criteria 1 (Societal Challenges) and 2 (Design at scale) during the problem definition and design stages (*when*) because of the potential to identify benefits that may arise from the NbS and subsequently spot trade-off and conflicting conditions (Coletta et al., 2021; Giordano et al., 2020).

Key stakeholders (*who*) include landowners who provide land for NbS because of the tendency for them to view NbS as a limitation to their economic gains (Lupp et al., 2021). Mediators and academics are also a core group. Researchers can conduct further analysis to ascertain the links between the various views and use techniques such as multi-criteria decision analysis and causal loop diagrams to assign a quantitative weight to different choices to aid deliberation (Coletta et al., 2021). Thus, consulting academics could help discuss the trade-offs because they are often perceived as neutral actors (Lupp et al., 2021).

Involvement and collaboration could be the most appropriate pathways (*how*) to engage the stakeholders under this criterion. Stakeholders such as landowners need collaboration and delegation to explore and better understand how NbS could provide benefits (Lupp et al., 2021). In the EU-funded project NAIAD, engagement occurred in stages with interviews occurring before workshops (Coletta et al., 2021). Interviews helped to initially understand the individual views of NbS benefits and challenges, while workshops enabled group discussion, ranking of benefits, evaluation of shared views and trade-offs (*how and why*). Similarly, in the Munich Isar Plan Kiss et al. (2022), consultation with citizens through interviews revealed that the younger and older generations had different preferences (*how, who and why*). The former preferred gravelling of riverbanks, while the latter favored grasslands. Hence, 30 % of the river was widened, while 60 % of meadows were maintained to cater for their respective needs.

3.7. Adaptive management

The engagement rationale (*why*) includes improving learning and

gaining stakeholder perceptions and views about NbS performance (Menny et al., 2018; van der Jagt et al., 2023). Key stakeholders (*who*) include citizens and non-governmental organisations usually engaged in the actual evaluation rather than designing the evaluation process.

The main pathway (*how*) is consultation with citizens who can provide feedback for evaluating various aspects of the NbS. Key methods for engagement include questionnaires, interviews, participant observations, travel diaries and workshops (Menny et al., 2018). The latter two were prevalent for collaborating and delegating pathways. The dominance of consultation is not necessarily because it is the most suitable form of engagement. However, it is because evaluation goals were pre-defined.

Consulting local communities could provide insights on incentivizing citizens to support implementation and monitoring (*how, who and why*). In Wolong's example, consultation with communities incentivized households to drive citizen-led monitoring of illegal logging as part of NbS implementation (Martin et al., 2021). There can also be collaboration and delegation for citizens to offer their labor in maintenance and implementation. For instance, in Mexico City's Water Forest and Chinampas for ecosystem restoration (Kiss et al., 2022), there were collective community initiatives to enhance livelihoods and ecosystem services such as water purification and flood regulation. In Cape Town, women were employed to help remove invasive species to preserve their catchment (Kiss et al., 2022). Finally, collaborating with communities can attract the support of voluntary groups in project maintenance. Such support could reduce maintenance costs and enhance social relationships between communities and NbS projects (Willems et al., 2020).

3.8. Sustainability and mainstreaming

Different case studies provide different rationales (*why*) for engaging stakeholders under this criterion. One such rationale is realizing the transformative potential of NbS and delivering a transformational impact at the system level (Malekpour et al., 2021; Menny et al., 2018). The transformation includes effecting fundamental change, effectively addressing societal challenges, and initiating sustainable innovations. Engagement could influence higher-level planning and policy frameworks to upscale NbS. Another rationale is to boost wider stakeholders' confidence and acceptance to support NbS replication (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016; Menny et al., 2018).

Higher-level engagement with stakeholders with decision-making powers (*who*) is particularly relevant to realise transformative goals (Malekpour et al., 2021; Menny et al., 2018). Moreover, scientists can examine NbS performance and provide evidence regarding the outcomes across scales (Raymond et al., 2017). Stakeholders with decision-making powers include investors, policymakers and planners who can function as "mediators, translators and networkers" (Frantzeskaki et al., 2017, p. 83). Hence, these stakeholders could be engaged through collaboration and delegation (*how*). For instance, planners and authorities could help integrate NbS into planning regulations and develop guidelines and directions for mainstreaming NbS across planning scales and sectors (*who and why*) (Raymond et al., 2017). In the Genk City Region's NbS initiative (Frantzeskaki et al., 2017), city administrators supported upscaling and mainstreaming by providing infrastructure, personnel and educational tools once it was evident that the NbS attracted more visitors. Similarly, a report by the Stockholm County Council Planning Division regarding the value of NbS triggered debates about local and urban development, which subsequently led to the "Protect the green wedges of Metropolitan Stockholm" network (Frantzeskaki et al., 2017, p. 80).

Engaging investors could commence through consultation and information provision before moving up the participation spectrum (*who and how*). Successful exemplar projects can help introduce NbS models and business strategies into the market (*why*). For instance, the Velt Genk & the Local Organic Allotment Gardens (Frantzeskaki et al., 2017) were initiated by citizens as a not-for-project measure. However, the

project later attracted partnerships and funding for widespread replication because the success of previous measures was clearly proven.

In the NbS initiative of City-Region Dresden, Germany (Frantzeskaki et al., 2017), umbrella organisations and cooperatives helped to connect small-scale NbS projects, including new and existing ones (*who and why*). Such stakeholders could mediate between individual NbS initiatives and local governments to enable knowledge sharing and embed NbS concept into the local government initiatives. Hence, such stakeholders can be consulted and collaborated with to help mainstream NbS (*how and why*).

Nevertheless, the general citizens could also be instrumental in providing information regarding previous implementation, including assistance in identifying areas where NbS could be replicated (*who and why*) (Raymond et al., 2017). Hence, citizens can be informed and consulted (*how*). Also, even if involving citizens would not necessarily result in transformation, engagement is needed for ethical, just and inclusivity reasons (Menny et al., 2018).

4. Discussion: implications for planning, resourcing and enabling transformative management of nature

This paper presents a framework for engaging stakeholders through the lens of the IUCN Global Standard for implementing NbS (Fig. 1). The IUCN standard provides both aspiration and guidance to operationalise nature-based solutions globally (Le Gouvello et al., 2023; Mehta et al., 2023) and this paper seeks to support its application by strengthening deliberate stakeholder engagement. In addition, growing emphasis on stakeholder engagement in NbS highlights the need for emerging co-creation approaches (e.g. European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023) to consider the complex themes that shape such engagement. By structuring this through the IUCN criteria, we propose a holistic approach to mainstream NbS within the socio-ecological system, fostering inclusive and adaptive solutions.

We show that stakeholder engagement should not be limited to one NbS topic (criterion 5, inclusivity) but considered pertinent to all aspects of NbS. It is important to deliberately consider the '*why, who, how and when*' to engage for every IUCN criterion since each reflects important principles for societally and environmentally resilient management of nature. There are also opportunities to learn from related fields focusing on stakeholder engagement practices as part of wider approaches to increase effectiveness (Caro-Gonzalez et al., 2023; Nita et al., 2022). However, our paper makes a novel contribution by providing an operational framework to widen stakeholder engagement to all NbS criteria, using the full range of engagement practices, comprising the rationale for engagement (*why*) (e.g. Kiss et al., 2022), project cycles (*when*) (e.g. Fors et al., 2021); the kind of stakeholders to engage (*who*) (e.g. Ferreira et al., 2020); and the manner of engagement (*how*) (e.g. Mahmoud and Morello, 2021).

Making these building blocks of stakeholder engagement an explicit and essential part of implementing NbS has several implications for practice, research and policy. Implementing the approach will need skills in stakeholder analysis, facilitation, relationship building and adaptive governance; and dealing with the potential politics involved in the *why, who, when and how* decisions will require time and patience. When designing stakeholder engagement, the project team should first consider the IUCN criteria to determine the range of issues around which stakeholders have interest and influence and establish a clear rationale (*why*) for engaging stakeholders. Afterwards, they should articulate and document expectations about stakeholders (*who*), project stages (*when*), and pathways (*how*) for engagement around each criterion. This process will aid collective clarity and inform planning for those charged with developing NbS. This complements well other studies and guidance on stakeholder engagement in and for NbS (Arlati et al., 2021; Fors et al., 2015; Jansson et al., 2020; Mahmoud and Morello, 2018) whose framing in terms of project development especially gives attention to '*when*'.

The fact that all aspects of engagement need to be considered across

all eight NbS criteria highlights that engagement is not only for facilitators or social scientists, as discussing biodiversity net-gain or balancing trade-offs will require ecologists, engineers and economists to engage with stakeholders in these debates. A transdisciplinary approach within a socio-ecological system helps to improve delivery but is complex and challenging (Bergmann et al., 2021; Tzoulas et al., 2021). It requires all project members to develop new competencies and commit to ongoing adaptive learning, potentially displacing experts and reshaping roles and responsibilities (Funtowicz and Ravetz, 1993). For society to fully enable and benefit from NbS, devolving and sharing responsibilities for decisions is critical (Giordano et al., 2020; Mitincu et al., 2023). Presently, NbS is often thought of as projects led by staff in regional government or civil society organisations (Kiss et al., 2022), but strengthening engagement and enabling empowerment may ultimately alter and widen who is considered part of the NbS team.

Reflexive and situational approaches are required by all those involved to address and adapt to difficult and competing circumstances during engagement processes (Kiss et al., 2022; Murunga, 2022). It may require difficult choices, such as balancing the demands of biodiversity advocates with funders' concerns and making hidden tensions more visible. Much of the NbS literature does not explicitly discuss power asymmetries and conflicting philosophies on how to manage nature (Spash, 2022). Reflection on the likely challenges of engagement, as enabled by this framework, makes visible some of the wicked problems (Termeer et al., 2015) that underpin the recurring challenges with both NbS and other systemic approaches. When NbS are framed as the means to bridge biodiversity conservation and economic development (Maes and Jacobs, 2017), the clash between these paradigms often underpins the challenges found, such as conflicting perspectives or material interests; lack of political support, resistance or apathy by key stakeholders; and lack of resources or funding. These are not issues that individual NbS projects can completely or easily resolve.

Policymakers and funders seeking to implement NbS on a landscape scale could use our framework to guide a more ambitious approach to stakeholder engagement from those planning, implementing and managing NbS. Thus, project leads should be able to justify their approaches to engagement by specifying the core rationales driving their engagement and ensuring all relevant stakeholders are engaged appropriately across the project phases. This requirement could ensure that project leads take engagement seriously and adopt systematic approaches to spot and involve stakeholders who might be hitherto ignored when the landscape context of NbS becomes more complex.

Moreover, findings should prompt the IUCN (and similar standards promoting upscaling of NbS) to clarify the complex realities of engaging stakeholders and emphasise how the inclusivity criterion overlaps all NbS criteria. These include the different stages and pathways for engaging stakeholders based on their needs across all NbS criteria. As mentioned earlier, stakeholder engagement for implementing NbS in the landscape involves working with and balancing different views and needs. What we present can help better plan how to do this, but this is a complex social process, and underlying power dynamics may not always be obvious to work with. Therefore, understanding more about the interacting nature of the NbS criteria may influence the framework and require a lot of capacity and energy.

Policymakers, funders and practitioners should know that deepening engagement per our framework will not necessarily make NbS projects easier, faster or cheaper. Indeed, it may require more careful planning, wider engagement, and more adaptive management (revising and reworking ideas where conflicts emerge). However, the framework offers an opportunity to openly discuss how full-scale stakeholder engagement in large-scale NbS might work. Those who seek to enable or fund NbS should recognise this implication. Our framework may also require a considerable budget to be spent on these activities, such that potentially a significant proportion of the project budget, whether from private, public or non-governmental sources, may need to be earmarked to support stakeholder engagement across the eight themes of the

Standard.

Deepening attention to stakeholder engagement is not something to evade, even though at first glance, it may make projects more challenging and ‘messy’, with higher demands on human capacity and resourcing. Given the scale and pace with which we need to work to respond to the climate and biodiversity crises, this should be seen as an investment in our future. NbS as a concept and practice is gaining ground because of its potential to help societies address the myriad challenges based on the range of ecosystem services such as climate regulation or safeguarding freshwater quality and biodiversity (Eggermont et al., 2015; Faivre et al., 2017; IPBES, 2019); therefore taking the time and resource to ensure this is done in a just manner, that increases societal support and builds collaboration instead of conflict, should be seen as necessary part of achieving the standard.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a framework to guide stakeholder engagement using the IUCN Standard for NbS. We demonstrate how each of the eight NbS criteria under the Standard provides important themes for planning stakeholder engagement. For each criterion, the framework prompts explicit reflection on the rationale (why), different stages of NbS development (when), stakeholders (who) and pathways (how) for engagement. This framework should enable those directly charged with implementing NbS – and those who enable and influence NbS – to reflect on and improve existing engagement practices. It may also provide the basis for analysis and research in stakeholder engagement in NbS.

We offer this first framework to strengthen the work of NbS development with and for society while whilst acknowledging that it may have limitations that need further testing and development. Also, given the limited NbS literature addressing stakeholder engagement, we drew on wider literature related to environmental management. Therefore, it will be valuable for future work to test the application of the framework and refine it further based on the different enablers and limitations of stakeholder engagement. There may also be an opportunity to deepen attention to issues such as justice and equity using approaches such as political ecology.

The framework should not be understood solely as something that can be easily ‘done’ or solve all challenges related to upscaling the implementation of nature-based solutions. Instead, more resources may be entailed to reflect and enable engagements. The practical resourcing implications of adopting such a comprehensive framework for stakeholder engagement should be highlighted to NbS researchers, practitioners and project funders. Even with this, there may be difficult implications – e.g. if resultant problem framings evolve away from top-down priorities and mandates – which highlight the need for more attention on the environmental and socio-political contexts that shape the expectations and mandates of what NbS should be and achieve.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alhassan Ibrahim: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original draft, Writing – review & editing & Visualization, Project administration. **Keith Marshall:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Validation. **Esther Carmen:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Validation. **Kirsty L. Blackstock:** Funding, Conceptualisation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Validation. **Kerry A. Waylen:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Validation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103971](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103971).

Data availability

Uploaded supplementary material 1, illustrating the literature used for the paper.

References

- Akhmouch, A., Clavreul, D., 2017. Towards inclusive water governance: oecd evidence and key principles of stakeholder engagement in the water sector. In *Freshwater Governance for the 21st Century*. Springer, Cham, pp. 29–49.
- European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation Andersson, I., Ferreira, I., Arlati, A., Bradley, S., Buijs, A., Van der Jagt, S. (2023). ,Guidelines for co-creation and co-governance of nature-based solutions – Insights from EU-funded projects. Publications Office of the European Union..
- Arlati, A., Rödl, A., Kanjaria-Christian, S., Knieling, J., 2021. Stakeholder participation in the planning and design of nature-based solutions. insights from CLEVER cities project in Hamburg. *Sustainability* 13 (5), 2572.
- Ayala-Orozco, B., Rosell, J.A., Merçon, J., Bueno, I., Alatorre-Frenk, G., Langle-Flores, A., Lobato, A., 2018. Challenges and strategies in place-based multi-stakeholder collaboration for sustainability: learning from experiences in the Global South. *Sustainability* 10 (9), 3217.
- Bächtiger, A., Dryzek, J.S., Mansbridge, J., Warren, M., 2018. Deliberative democracy. *The Oxford handbook of deliberative democracy*, 1–32.
- Bark, R.H., Martin-Ortega, J., Waylen, K.A., 2021. Stakeholders’ views on natural flood management: implications for the nature-based solutions paradigm shift? *Environ. Sci. Policy* 115, 91–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.10.018>.
- Bergmann, M., Schöpke, N., Marg, O., Stelzer, F., Lang, D.J., Bossert, M., Sußmann, N., 2021. Transdisciplinary sustainability research in real-world labs: success factors and methods for change. *Sustain. Sci.* 16 (2), 541–564. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00886-8>.
- Blackstock, K.L., Richards, C., 2007. Evaluating stakeholder involvement in river basin planning: a Scottish case study. *Water Policy* 9 (5), 493–512.
- Blackstock, K.L., Waylen, K.A., Marshall, K.M., Dunglinson, J., 2014. Hybridity of representation: insights from river basin management planning in Scotland. *Environ. Plan. C: Gov. Policy* 32 (3), 549–566. <https://doi.org/10.1068/c11261>.
- Calliari, E., Staccione, A., Mysiak, J., 2019. An assessment framework for climate-proof nature-based solutions. *Sci. Total Environ.* 656, 691–700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.11.341>.
- Cantergiani, C., Herranz, K., Murphy-Evans, N., Bradley, S., Pastours, J., Menny, M., Berrini, M., 2019. Co-creation plan and co-design. *Solut. CALS*.
- Caro-Gonzalez, A.L., Nita, A., Toro, J., Zamorano, M., 2023. From procedural to transformative: a review of the evolution of effectiveness in EIA. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 103, 107256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2023.107256>.
- Châles, F., Bellanger, M., Bailly, D., Dutra, L.X., Pendleton, L., 2023. Using standards for coastal nature-based solutions in climate commitments: applying the IUCN global standard to the case of Pacific small Island developing states. *Nat. Based Solut.* 3, 100034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2022.100034>.
- Cohen-Shacham, E., Andrade, A., Dalton, J., Dudley, N., Jones, M., Kumar, C., Walters, G., 2019. Core principles for successfully implementing and upscaling nature-based solutions. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 98, 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.04.014>.
- Cohen-Shacham, E., Walters, G., Janzen, C., Maginnis, S., 2016. Nature-based solutions to address global societal challenges, 97. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland, pp. 2016–2036.

- Coletta, V.R., Pagano, A., Pluchinotta, I., Fratino, U., Scricieci, A., Nanu, F., Giordano, R., 2021. Causal loop diagrams for supporting nature based solutions participatory design and performance assessment. *J. Environ. Manag.* 280, 111668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.111668>.
- Convention on Biological Diversity, 2000. Sustaining life on earth: how the convention on biological diversity promotes nature and human well-being. *Secr. Conv. Biol. Divers.*
- Convention on Wetlands, 2021. Global guidelines for peatland rewetting and restoration. Gland, Switz. *Secr. Conv. Wetl.*
- Dennis, M., James, P., 2016. User participation in urban green commons: exploring the links between access, voluntarism, biodiversity and well being. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 15, 22–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2015.11.009>.
- van der Jagt, A.P.N., Buijs, A., Dobbs, C., van Lierop, M., Pauleit, S., Randrup, T.B., Wild, T., 2023. An action framework for the participatory assessment of nature-based solutions in cities. *Ambio* 52 (1), 54–67. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-022-01772-6>.
- van der Jagt, A., Tozer, L., Toxopeus, H., Runhaar, H., 2023. Policy mixes for mainstreaming urban nature-based solutions: an analysis of six European countries and the European union. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 139, 51–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.10.011>.
- Eggermont, H., Balian, E., Azevedo, J.M.N., Beumer, V., Brodin, T., Claudet, J., Le Roux, X., 2015. Nature-based solutions: new influence for environmental management and research in Europe. *GAIA - Ecol. Perspect. Sci. Soc.* 24 (4), 243–248. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.24.4.9>.
- Egusquiza, A., Cortese, M., Perfido, D., 2019. Mapping of innovative governance models to overcome barriers for nature based urban regeneration. *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 323 (1), 012081. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/323/1/012081>.
- Faivre, N., Fritz, M., Freitas, T., de Boissezon, B., Vandewoestijne, S., 2017. Nature-based solutions in the EU: innovating with nature to address social, economic and environmental challenges. *Environ. Res.* 159, 509–518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.08.032>.
- Ferreira, V., Barreira, A.P., Loures, L., Antunes, D., Panagopoulos, T., 2020. Stakeholders' engagement on nature-based solutions: a systematic literature review. *Sustainability* 12 (2), 640.
- Fisher, D., Blackstock, K., Irvine, K., 2021. It's on the 'nice to have' pile": potential principles to improve the implementation of socially inclusive green infrastructure. *Ambio* 50 (8), 1574–1586. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-020-01372-2>.
- Fors, H., Hagemann, F.A., Sang, Å.O., Randrup, T.B., 2021. Striving for inclusion—a systematic review of long-term participation in strategic management of urban green spaces. *Front. Sustain. Cities* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2021.572423>.
- Fors, H., Molin, J.F., Murphy, M.A., Konijnendijk van den Bosch, C., 2015. User participation in urban green spaces – for the people or the parks? *Urban For. Urban Green.* 14 (3), 722–734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2015.05.007>.
- Frantzeskaki, N., Borgström, S., Gorissen, L., Eggermann, M., Ehnert, F., 2017. Nature-based solutions accelerating urban sustainability transitions in cities: lessons from Dresden, Genk and Stockholm cities. *Nat. -Based Solut. Clim. Change Adapt. Urban Area. Link. Sci. Policy Pract.* 65–88.
- Frantzeskaki, N., Bush, J., 2021. Governance of nature-based solutions through intermediaries for urban transitions – a case study from Melbourne, Australia. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 64, 127262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127262>.
- Funtowicz, S.O., Ravetz, J.R., 1993. Science for the post-normal age. *Futures* 25 (7), 739–755. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287\(93\)90022-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287(93)90022-L).
- Giordano, R., Pluchinotta, I., Pagano, A., Scricieci, A., Nanu, F., 2020. Enhancing nature-based solutions acceptance through stakeholders' engagement in co-benefits identification and trade-offs analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* 713, 136552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136552>.
- IAP2. (2018). IAP2 spectrum of public participation. In: International Association for Public Participation Thornton, CO.
- Ibrahim, A., Bartsch, K., Sharifi, E., 2020. Green infrastructure needs green governance: Lessons from Australia's largest integrated stormwater management project, the River Torrens Linear Park. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 121202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121202>.
- Ibrahim, A., Bartsch, K., Sharifi, E., 2023. Waterways transformation and green stormwater infrastructure: enabling governance for Adelaide's River Torrens catchment, Australia. *Int. J. Water Resour. Dev.* <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900627.2022.2163624>.
- IPBES, 2019. Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. I. secretariat, Bonn, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>.
- IUCN, 2020b. IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions. A user-friendly framework for the verification, design and scaling up of NbS. First edition. IUCN, International Union for the Conservation of Nature, Gland, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2020.08.en>.
- IUCN, 2020a. Guidance for using the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions: first edition. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2020.09.en>.
- Jansson, M., Vogel, N., Fors, H., Dempsey, N., Buijs, A., Randrup, T.B., 2020. Defining urban open space governance and management. In *Urban open space governance and management*. Routledge.
- Juárez-Bourke, A., Blackstock, K.L., 2021. Participatory approaches: principles and practices for river restoration projects. *River Restor. Political Soc. Econ. Perspect.* 294–307.
- Kiss, B., Sekulova, F., Horschelmann, K., Salk, C.F., Takahashi, W., Wamsler, C., 2022. Citizen participation in the governance of nature-based solutions. *Environ. Policy Gov.* 32 (3), 247–272. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1987>.
- de Koning, S., Boezeman, D., Kaufmann, M., Visseren-Hamakers, I.J., 2023. Transformative change for biodiversity: a review on the contribution of landscape-oriented partnerships. *Biol. Conserv.* 277, 109858. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109858>.
- Kotsila, P., Anguelovski, I., Baró, F., Langemeyer, J., Sekulova, F., JT Connolly, J., 2021. Nature-based solutions as discursive tools and contested practices in urban nature's neoliberalisation processes. *Environ. Plan. E Nat. Space* 4 (2), 252–274.
- Le Gouvello, R., Cohen-Shacham, E., Herr, D., Spadone, A., Simard, F., Brugere, C., 2023. The IUCN global standard for nature-based solutions™ as a tool for enhancing the sustainable development of marine aquaculture. *Front. Mar. Sci.*
- Lupp, G., Huang, J.J., Zingraff-Hamed, A., Oen, A., Del Sepia, N., Martinelli, A., Pauleit, S., 2021. Stakeholder perceptions of nature-based solutions and their collaborative co-design and implementation processes in rural mountain areas—a case study from PHUSICOS. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.678446>.
- Mabon, L., Barkved, L., de Bruin, K., Shih, W.-Y., 2022. Whose knowledge counts in nature-based solutions? Understanding epistemic justice for nature-based solutions through a multi-city comparison across Europe and Asia. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 136, 652–664. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.07.025>.
- Maes, J., Jacobs, S., 2017. Nature-based solutions for Europe's sustainable development. *Conserv. Lett.* 10 (1), 121–124. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12216>.
- Mahmoud, I., Morello, E., 2018. Co-Creation Pathway as a catalyst for implementing nature-based solution in urban regeneration strategies learning from CLEVER cities framework and Milano as test-bed. *Urban. Inf.* 278 (3), 204–210.
- Mahmoud, I.H., Morello, E., Ludlow, D., Salvia, G., 2021. Co-creation pathways to inform shared governance of urban living labs in practice: lessons from three European projects. *Front. Sustain. Cities* 3, 690458.
- Mahmoud, I., & Morello, E. (2021). Co-creation pathway for urban Nature-based Solutions: Testing a shared governance approach in three cities and nine action labs.
- Malekpour, S., Tawfik, S., Chesterfield, C., 2021. Designing collaborative governance for nature-based solutions. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 62, 127177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127177>.
- Martin, J.G.C., Scolobig, A., Linnerooth-Bayer, J., Liu, W., Balsiger, J., 2021. Catalyzing innovation: governance enablers of nature-based solutions. *Sustainability* 13 (4), 1971. Retrieved from. (<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/4/1971>).
- Mayor, B., Toxopeus, H., McQuaid, S., Croci, E., Lucchitta, B., Reddy, S.E., López Gunn, E., 2021. State of the art and latest advances in exploring business models for nature-based solutions. *Sustainability* 13 (13), 7413. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137413>.
- Meadow, A.M., Ferguson, D.B., Guido, Z., Horangic, A., Owen, G., Wall, T., 2015. Moving toward the deliberate coproduction of climate science knowledge. *Weather Clim. Soc.* 7 (2), 179–191.
- Mehta, D., Pandey, R., Kumar Gupta, A., Juhola, S., 2023. Nature-based solutions in Hindu Kush Himalayas: IUCN global standard based synthesis. *Ecol. Indic.* 154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.110875>.
- Menny, M., Palgan, Y.V., McCormick, K., 2018. Urban living labs and the role of users in co-creation. *GAIA-Ecol. Perspect. Sci. Soc.* 27 (1), 68–77.
- Mitincu, C.-G., Niță, M.-R., Hossu, C.-A., Iojă, I.-C., Nita, A., 2023. Stakeholders' involvement in the planning of nature-based solutions: a network analysis approach. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 141, 69–79.
- Mok, S., Mačiulytė, E., Bult, P.H., Hawxwell, T., 2021. Valuing the invaluable (?)—a framework to facilitate stakeholder engagement in the planning of nature-based solutions. *Sustainability* 13 (5), 2657.
- dos Muchangos, L.S., Tokai, A., Hanashima, A., 2017. Stakeholder analysis and social network analysis to evaluate the stakeholders of a MSWM system—a pilot study of Maputo City. *Environ. Dev.* 24, 124–135.
- Murunga, M., 2022. Public engagement for social transformation: informing or empowering? *Environ. Sci. Policy* 132, 237–246.
- Nita, A., Fineran, S., Rozyłowicz, L., 2022. Researchers' perspective on the main strengths and weaknesses of environmental impact assessment (EIA) procedures. *Environ. Impact Assess. Rev.* 92, 106690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2021.106690>.
- OECD, 2015a. OECD principles on water governance. OECD, Paris, France.
- OECD, 2015b. Stakeholder Engagement for Inclusive Water Governance.
- Palomo, I., Locatelli, B., Otero, I., Colloff, M., Crouzat, E., Cuni-Sanchez, A., Jiménez-Aceituno, A., 2021. Assessing nature-based solutions for transformative change. *One Earth* 4 (5), 730–741.
- Puskás, N., Abunnasr, Y., Naalbandian, S., 2021. Assessing deeper levels of participation in nature-based solutions in urban landscapes—a literature review of real-world cases. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 210, 104065.
- Raymond, C.M., Frantzeskaki, N., Kabisch, N., Berry, P., Breil, M., Nita, M.R., Calfapietra, C., 2017. A framework for assessing and implementing the co-benefits of nature-based solutions in urban areas. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 77, 15–24.
- Reed, M.S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Stringer, L.C., 2009. Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *J. Environ. Manag.* 90 (5), 1933–1949.
- Seddon, N., Chausson, A., Berry, P., Girardin, C.A., Smith, A., Turner, B., 2020. Understanding the value and limits of nature-based solutions to climate change and other global challenges. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B* 375 (1794), 20190120. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0120>.
- Seddon, N., Smith, A., Smith, P., Key, I., Chausson, A., Girardin, C., Turner, B., 2021. Getting the message right on nature-based solutions to climate change. *Glob. Change Biol.* 27 (8), 1518–1546.
- Sequeira, D., Warner, M., 2007. Stakeholder engagement: a good practice handbook for companies doing business in emerging markets. IFC E&S & The World Bank, Washington, D.C. Retrieved from. (<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publicati>

- on/documents-reports/documentdetail/579261468162552212/stakeholder-engagement-a-good-practice-handbook-for-companies-doing-business-in-emerging-markets).
- Spash, C.L., 2022. Conservation in conflict: corporations, capitalism and sustainable development. *Biol. Conserv.* 269, 109528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109528>.
- Stirling, A., 2006. Analysis, participation and power: justification and closure in participatory multi-criteria analysis. *Land Use Policy* 23 (1), 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2004.08.010>.
- Stirling, A., 2007. Opening up” and “closing down: power, participation, and pluralism in the social appraisal of technology. *Sci. Technol. Hum. Values - Sci. Technol. Hum. Val.* 33, 262–294. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243907311265>.
- Termeer, C.J.A.M., Dewulf, A., Breeman, G., Stiller, S.J., 2015. Governance capabilities for dealing wisely with wicked problems. *Adm. Soc.* 47 (6), 680–710. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399712469195>.
- Tzoulas, K., Galan, J., Venn, S., Dennis, M., Pedroli, B., Mishra, H., James, P., 2021. A conceptual model of the social–ecological system of nature-based solutions in urban environments. *Ambio* 50 (2), 335–345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-020-01380-2>.
- UN ESCAP, 2009. What is good governance? In: United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific.
- UNEP, 2022. Resolution Adopted by the United Nations Environment Assembly on 2 March 2022. Nature-Based Solutions for Supporting Sustainable Development. United Nations Environment Assembly of the United Nations Environment Programme Fifth session. Retrieved from. (<https://www.unep.org/environmentasse> mbly/unea-5.2/outcomes-resumed-session-unea-5-unea-5.2-0?%2Funea-5_2%2Fproceedings-report-ministerial-declaration-resolutions-and-decisions-unea-5.2).
- Vogler, D., Macey, S., Sigouin, A., 2017. Stakeholder analysis in environmental and conservation planning. *Lessons Conserv.* 7 (7), 5–16.
- Walker, B., Holling, C.S., Carpenter, S.R., Kinzig, A., 2004. Resilience, adaptability and transformability in social–ecological systems. *Ecol. Soc.* 9 (2). Retrieved from. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26267673>.
- Waylen, K.A., Blackstock, K.L., Marshall, K.B., Dunglison, J., 2015. Participation–prescription tension in natural resource management: the case of diffuse pollution in Scottish water management. *Environ. Policy Gov.* 25 (2), 111–124.
- Welden, E.A., Chausson, A., Melanidis, M.S., 2021. Leveraging nature-based solutions for transformation: reconnecting people and nature. *People Nat.* 3 (5), 966–977. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10212>.
- Willems, J.J., Molenveld, A., Voorberg, W., Brinkman, G., 2020. Diverging ambitions and instruments for citizen participation across different stages in green infrastructure projects. *Urban Plan.* 5 (1), 22–32.
- Woroniecki, S., Wendo, H., Brink, E., Islar, M., Krause, T., Vargas, A.-M., Mahmoud, Y., 2020. Nature unsettled: how knowledge and power shape ‘nature-based’ approaches to societal challenges. *Glob. Environ. Change* 65, 102132.
- WWAP, 2018. The United Nations World Water Development Report 2018: Nature-based solutions for water. United Nations. UNESCO, Paris.
- Zingraff-Hamed, A., Hüesker, F., Lupp, G., Begg, C., Huang, J., Oen, A., Pauleit, S., 2020. Stakeholder mapping to co-create nature-based solutions: who is on board? *Sustainability* 12 (20), 8625.